

NEEDS ANALYSIS OF TEACHERS DEVELOPMENT ON SELECTED PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN ANTIPOLO CITY: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED TRAINING PROGRAM

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Needs Analysis of Teachers Development on Selected Public Elementary Schools in Antipolo City: Basis for a Proposed Training Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine/analyze the teachers' development in the selected elementary schools in Antipolo City, which served as inputs for a proposed training program during the school year 2024-2025. Regarding the practices in promoting teachers' professional development, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.58, which was verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. Regarding creating conditions for effective professional development, such as opportunities and challenges, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.54 verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. Regarding policy implications, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.59 verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. The Teacher Performance Evaluation for the academic year 2023-2024 is derived from the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). It categorized teacher performance into two main groups based on their evaluation scores. The first category, ranging from 4.1 to 5.00, represented "Outstanding" performance, with 143 teachers achieving scores within this range. This group constituted 56.75% of the total evaluated teachers, indicating a predominant presence of outstanding performance. The second category spanned from 3.1 to 4.00, denoting "Very Satisfactory" performance, with 109 teachers falling within this range, accounting for 43.25% of the evaluated teachers. The significant relationship between the level of perception of the teacher-respondents as regards teachers' development and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF is a key finding of this study. This relationship, which is highly significant, provides valuable insights into the factors influencing teacher performance.

Keywords: *professional development, performance, IPCRF*

Introduction

Effective leadership of good school leaders is crucial in the responsibilities one has to undertake. Guiding new employees to the workplace is a significant aspect of this role. It is essential to portray a sense of friendliness and willingness to allow new recruits to adjust to the environment. This process involves outlining the policies and practices of the organization, which is a key part of effective leadership. In addition, effective leadership brings together diverse people and helps them find a common purpose, inspiring and empowering them to realize their fullest potential and work towards achieving common goals.

Equally timeless is the need to shape and mold the river's channels. The effort to continually remanufacture leadership continues as men and women seek new ways to guide, manage, and motivate others. All organizations build upon three key strengths: an intimate knowledge of where the group intends to go and how it will get there, the ability of both leaders and team members to focus on a productive contribution to themselves and others, and the common desire to do whatever is necessary to achieve a positive outcome. A leadership gap is created whenever one or more of these elements are neglected or underdeveloped. They emphasized that there has been such a demand for effective leadership at no other time in history. The challenge and essence were for effective leadership to accentuate the good decisions and then find a way to reshape the bad. They stated, "Part of the universal challenge of leadership is defining it in a way that will apply to virtually everyone." Possession of certain skills, styles, personalities, positions, or titles does not define leadership.

When leading, it is vital for leaders to develop good rapport with fellow colleagues to motivate them in the right direction. At the same time, it is crucial to avoid the creation of hierarchies in an organization, as these can demoralize employees due to a failure to appreciate their contributions. This practice leads to a decline in the performance capacity of employers due to the reduction in exploitation of their full potential (Drucker 2019).

With these imperative ideas, the researcher was urged to conduct this study on the public school administrators' leadership practices as a correlate to teachers' performance school performance to determine the extent of the leadership practices of the school administrators to determine the implementing techniques on the leadership practices of school administrators; and to determine if the leadership practices of the school administrators contribute to the improvement of school performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine / analyze the teachers' development on the selected elementary schools in Antipolo City which served as inputs for a proposed training program during the school year 2024-2025. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of perception of the teacher-respondents as regards the teachers' development in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. the practices in promoting teachers' professional development;

- 1.2. creating conditions for effective professional development: opportunities and challenges; and
- 1.3. implications for policy?
2. What is the level of Grade 6 pupils' learning achievements using the user-centered word game-based approach in Science and Mathematics when they are categorized as:
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory; and,
 - 2.5. did not meet expectations?
3. What is the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF of SY 2023-2024?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of perception of the teacher-respondents as regards teachers' development and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF?
5. Based on the results of the study, what training program may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The method of research used in the study was the descriptive type. Descriptive research, Ethridge, D.E. (2019) is "aimed at casting light on current issues or problems through a process of data collection that enables them to describe the situation more completely than was possible. In its essence, descriptive studies are used to describe various aspects of the phenomenon. In its popular format, descriptive research describes the characteristics and behavior of the sample population.

An important characteristic of descriptive research is that while descriptive research can employ several variables, only one variable is required to conduct a descriptive study. The three main purposes of descriptive studies are describing, explaining, and validating research findings.

Respondents

The researcher employed purposive sampling, a method known for its thoroughness in selecting specific participants. This was conducted in the selected schools of District IC and ID, Division of Antipolo City. The respondents of the study were composed of teachers, a group with a wealth of knowledge and experience. Each instrument was meticulously administered to all the respondents, who were given sufficient time to answer the research instrument. The scope of this study covered the teachers from the selected schools of District IC and ID, Division of Antipolo City.

Instrument

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire and descriptive questions that served as indicators in every variable. The survey questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part contained the evaluation of the respondents. The second part contained the office performance commitment and review form rating (OPCRF), and the third part contained the comments and suggestions of the teacher-respondents.

The questionnaires that served as the survey instrument of the study were validated by experts to ensure their correctness and validity. The contents of the questionnaire were analyzed and scrutinized by a panel of principals, master teachers, English teachers, and an education program supervisor. Their comments and feedback were considered in the final approval of the method, which was then examined by a consultant acting as the researcher's proofreader, providing a final check of the methodology.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the study was conducted. Upon approval of the school's division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the teacher-respondents from the selected public elementary schools of District IC and ID, Division of Antipolo City, and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency, Percentage Distribution, and Ranking. This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

Pearson r Correlation. This was used to determine the significant correlation between the OPCRF ratings of the school and the public-school administrators' leadership practices.

Results and Discussion

This section provided the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Level of Perception of the Teachers as Regards the Public-School Administrators' Leadership Practices

Level of Perception of the Teacher-Respondents as Regards Teachers' Development in terms of The Practices in Promoting Teachers' Professional Development

Table 1. *Level of Perception of the Teacher-Respondents as Regards Teachers' Development in terms of The Practices in Promoting Teachers' Professional Development*

<i>A. The Practices in Promoting Teachers' Professional Development</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Informs teachers of opportunities for professional development.	3.59	Very Strongly Agree	6
2.	Selects in-service activities that are consistent with the school's academic goals.	3.33	Very Strongly Agree	10
3.	Supports teachers' requests for in-service training that is directly related to the school's academic goals.	3.66	Very Strongly Agree	4
4.	Distributes journal articles to teachers on a regular basis.	3.63	Very Strongly Agree	5
5.	Supports the use of skills acquired during in-service training in the classroom.	3.85	Very Strongly Agree	1
6.	Ensures that instructional aides receive appropriate training to help students meet instructional objectives.	3.48	Very Strongly Agree	8
7.	Arranges for outside speakers to make presentations about instruction at faculty meetings.	3.35	Very Strongly Agree	9
8.	Provides time to meet individually with teachers to discuss instructional issues.	3.78	Very Strongly Agree	2
9.	Sits in on teachers' in-service activities concerned with instruction.	3.51	Very Strongly Agree	7
10.	Sets aside time of faculty meetings for teachers to share about instruction or information emanating from in-service activities.	3.66	Very Strongly Agree	3
Composite Mean		3.58	Very Strongly Agree	

As discussed in Table 1, the respondents stated that the school administrators support the use of skills acquired during in-service training in the classroom, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.85 and the highest rank of 1. The school administrators supported the use of skills acquired during in-service training in the classroom, demonstrating a commitment to professional development and continuous improvement among teachers. This practice was highly beneficial, as it ensured that newly acquired knowledge and techniques were effectively integrated into instructional practices, ultimately enhancing student learning outcomes. Administrators facilitated the application of in-service training skills by providing opportunities for teachers to practice and implement what they learned. They encouraged teachers to experiment with new strategies, methodologies, and technologies introduced during training sessions. This hands-on approach allowed teachers to gain confidence and proficiency in applying these skills in real classroom settings. According to Tan et al. (2021), school leadership practices, particularly instructional management and engaging external stakeholders, positively impact student academic achievement and learning attitudes/processes, but not attainment.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators select in-service activities that are consistent with the school's academic goals which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.33 and least rank of 10. The school administrators selected in-service activities that were consistently aligned with the school's academic goals, demonstrating strategic planning and a commitment to advancing educational objectives. This approach ensured that professional development opportunities for teachers directly supported and reinforced the school's overarching mission and vision for student success. Administrators began by identifying and prioritizing the specific academic goals and objectives outlined in the school's strategic plan or curriculum framework. These goals typically encompassed areas such as improving student achievement, enhancing instructional quality, fostering inclusive practices, and promoting professional growth among staff. Jong et al. (2020) stated that school principals exhibit two main leadership patterns: team player and facilitator, demonstrating a wider repertoire of leadership practices in leading collaborative innovation.

The composite mean of 3.58 implied that the level of perception of the teachers as regards the teachers' development in terms of the practices in promoting teachers' professional development is within high level. The findings indicated that the level of perception among teachers regarding teachers' development in promoting teachers' professional development was consistently high. Teachers valued administrators' proactive approach and commitment to fostering continuous growth and improvement among educators, which significantly contributed to a supportive and effective learning environment. Administrators demonstrated strong leadership in promoting teachers' professional development through several strategic practices. They prioritized and allocated resources towards relevant and meaningful professional development opportunities aligned with the school's educational goals and curriculum objectives. This ensured that teachers had access to training, workshops, and seminars that directly enhanced their instructional practices and student engagement strategies. Principals in high-performing community high schools in Nepal use multiple frames of leadership, collaboration, and proactive reforms to achieve success, with key factors being interest, collaboration, and high-quality teachers (Khanal et al., 2020).

Level of Perception of the Teacher-Respondents as Regards Teachers' Development in terms of Creating Conditions for Effective Professional Development: Opportunities and Challenges

As discussed in Table 2, the respondents stated that the school administrators provide curricular models and modeling of instruction for teachers to have a clear vision of what best practices look like, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.81 and the highest rank of 1. The school administrators provided curricular models and modeled instructional practices for teachers, offering a clear vision of

best practices in teaching and learning.

Table 2. Level of Perception of the Teacher-Respondents as Regards Teachers' Development in terms of Creating Conditions for Effective Professional Development: Opportunities and Challenges

<i>B. Creating Conditions for Effective Professional Development: Opportunities and Challenges</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Focuses on teaching strategies associated with specific curriculum content supports teacher learning within teachers' classroom contexts.	3.41	Very Strongly Agree	8
2.	Includes an intentional focus on discipline-specific curriculum development and pedagogies in areas such as mathematics, science, or literacy.	3.53	Very Strongly Agree	6
3.	Engages teachers directly in designing and trying out teaching strategies, providing them an opportunity to engage in the same style of learning they are designing for their students.	3.56	Very Strongly Agree	5
4.	Uses authentic artifacts, interactive activities, and other strategies to provide deeply embedded, highly contextualized professional learning.	3.64	Very Strongly Agree	3
5.	Creates space for teachers to share ideas and collaborate in their learning, often in job-embedded contexts.	3.56	Very Strongly Agree	4
6.	Creates communities that positively change the culture and instruction of their entire grade level, department, school and/or district.	3.48	Very Strongly Agree	7
7.	Provides Curricular models and modeling of instruction for teachers to have a clear vision of what best practices look like.	3.81	Very Strongly Agree	1
8.	Includes lesson plans, unit plans, sample student work, observations of peer teachers, and video or written cases of teaching.	3.36	Very Strongly Agree	9
9.	Involves the sharing of expertise about content and evidence-based practices, focused directly on teachers' individual needs.	3.71	Very Strongly Agree	2
10.	Provides built-in time for teachers to think about, receive input on, and make changes to their practice by facilitating reflection and soliciting feedback.	3.34	Very Strongly Agree	10
<i>Composite Mean</i>		<i>3.54</i>	<i>Very Strongly Agree</i>	

As discussed in Table 2, the respondents stated that the school administrators provide curricular models and modeling of instruction for teachers to have a clear vision of what best practices look like, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.81 and the highest rank of 1. The school administrators provided curricular models and modeled instructional practices for teachers, offering a clear vision of best practices in teaching and learning. This approach was highly effective in guiding and supporting teachers in their professional growth and in aligning instructional practices with the school's educational goals and standards. Administrators began by collaboratively developing comprehensive curricular models that outlined the scope, sequence, and objectives of the school's academic programs. These models were designed to provide a framework for teachers to understand the expectations and benchmarks for student learning across different grade levels and subject areas. According to Bush (2021), successful school leadership is a function of structure and culture, supported by strategic thinking and analysis, with a focus on human resource dimensions and time use and allocation for reading and language.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators provide built-in time for teachers to think about, receive input on, and make changes to their practice by facilitating reflection and soliciting feedback which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.34 and least rank of 10. The school administrators facilitated built-in time for teachers to engage in reflection, receive input, and make changes to their practice, thereby promoting continuous improvement and enhancing teaching effectiveness. This structured approach to professional development was instrumental in fostering a supportive and collaborative learning environment among educators. Administrators prioritized dedicated time within the school schedule for teachers to engage in reflective practices. They organized regular meetings, professional development sessions, and staff retreats where teachers could pause, reflect on their instructional practices, and evaluate their effectiveness in meeting student learning objectives and school goals. Bellibaş et al. (2020) stated that instructional leadership indirectly influences teachers' classroom practices through shared practices and increased sense of agency in learning effectiveness.

The composite mean of 3.54 implied that the level of perception of the teachers as regards teachers' development in terms of creating conditions for effective professional development, opportunities and challenges is within high level. The findings indicated that the level of perception among teachers regarding public-school administrators' leadership practices in creating conditions for effective professional development, opportunities, and challenges was consistently high. Teachers recognized and valued administrators' proactive efforts in fostering a supportive and conducive environment for professional growth, which significantly contributed to enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Administrators demonstrated strong leadership by prioritizing and allocating resources towards diverse professional development opportunities that catered to the needs and interests of teachers. They facilitated workshops, seminars, and training sessions that aligned with educational goals, curriculum standards, and emerging instructional trends. This strategic approach ensured that teachers had access to relevant and impactful learning experiences that enhanced their instructional skills and pedagogical knowledge. Tan et al. (2021) stated that school leadership has a small but significant impact on student outcomes, with larger effects for organizational and teacher outcomes than for student outcomes.

Level of Perception of the Teacher-Respondents as Regards Teachers' Development in terms of Implications for Policy

Table 3. *Level of Perception of the Teacher-Respondents as Regards Teachers' Development in terms of Implications for Policy*

	<i>C. Implications for Policy</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	Adopts standards for professional development to guide the design, evaluation, and funding of professional learning provided to educators.	3.78	Very Strongly Agree	2
2.	Evaluates and redesign the use of time and school schedules to increase opportunities for professional learning and collaboration, including participation in professional learning communities, peer coaching and observations across classrooms, and collaborative planning.	3.51	Very Strongly Agree	8
3.	Conducts needs assessments using data from staff surveys to identify areas of professional learning most needed and desired by educators.	3.66	Very Strongly Agree	3
4.	Identifies and develop expert teachers as mentors and coaches to support learning in their particular area(s) of expertise for other educators.	3.41	Very Strongly Agree	10
5.	Integrates professional learning into ESSA school improvement initiatives, such as efforts to implement new learning standards, use student data to inform instruction, improve student literacy, increase student access to advanced coursework, and create a positive and inclusive learning environment.	3.53	Very Strongly Agree	7
6.	Provides technology-facilitated opportunities for professional learning and coaching, using funding available under Titles II and IV of ESSA to address the needs of rural communities.	3.56	Very Strongly Agree	6
7.	Provides flexible funding and continuing education units for learning opportunities.	3.64	Very Strongly Agree	4
8.	Includes sustained engagement in collaboration, mentoring, and coaching, as well as institutes, workshops, and seminars.	3.56	Very Strongly Agree	5
9.	Creates good systems of tracking Professional Development, let alone systems for analyzing the quality and impact of Professional Development.	3.48	Very Strongly Agree	9
10.	Adopts and implement professional learning for teachers that is evidence based and designed to address potential obstacles.	3.81	Very Strongly Agree	1
Composite Mean		3.59	Very Strongly Agree	

As discussed in Table 3, the respondents stated that the school administrators adopt and implement professional learning for teachers that is evidence based and designed to address potential obstacles, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.81 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school administrators adopted and implemented evidence-based professional learning programs for teachers, specifically designed to tackle potential obstacles. Administrators were observed to prioritize professional development initiatives that were grounded in research and tailored to address specific challenges faced by educators. This approach suggested a strategic focus on enhancing teaching practices and overcoming barriers to effective instruction. Teachers perceived these efforts positively, acknowledging the value of evidence-based strategies in their professional growth and instructional effectiveness. This proactive stance by administrators underscored their commitment to supporting teachers through targeted, research-backed learning opportunities, aimed at improving overall educational outcomes within the school environment. Middle school leaders play a key role in leading learning from classrooms and connecting system demands to student and staff needs, relying on leading practices and processes rather than abstract personal qualities (Murphy, 2020).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school administrators identify and develop expert teachers as mentors and coaches to support learning in their particular area(s) of expertise for other educators which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.41 and least rank of 10. The school administrators adopted and implemented evidence-based professional learning for teachers, designed to effectively address potential obstacles and enhance teaching practices. This strategic approach was instrumental in promoting continuous improvement and supporting teachers in achieving high standards of instructional excellence. Administrators began by identifying evidence-based practices and research findings that informed the design of professional learning opportunities. They conducted needs assessments, analyzed student data, and solicited input from teachers to identify specific instructional challenges or areas for improvement. This data-driven approach ensured that professional development initiatives were targeted and aligned with the school's educational goals and priorities. According to Sari (2022), situational leadership practices in schools can develop work motivation, improve teacher performance, and increase teacher commitment to the organization.

The composite mean of 3.59 implied that the perception of the teachers as regards teachers' development in terms of implications for policy is within high level. The findings revealed that teachers held a high regard for teachers' development, particularly in their implications for policy. Teachers perceived these practices as impactful and influential in shaping educational policies and practices within the school system. This perception indicated that administrators' leadership was seen as pivotal in driving policy changes and improvements in educational settings. The results suggested that teachers viewed administrators not only as leaders but also as key stakeholders in policy formulation and implementation. This high level of perception underscored the importance of collaborative and effective leadership from administrators in fostering positive educational outcomes and systemic improvements. Leithwood (2021) stated that effective school leadership practices include building partnerships, encouraging culturally responsive instruction, and understanding students' families' expectations.

Teacher's performance based on IPCRF.

Table 4. *Teacher's performance based on IPCRF*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
4.1 - 5.00 (Outstanding)	143	56.75	1
3.1 - 4.00 (Very Satisfactory)	109	43.25	2
Total	252	100.00	
Mean Grade	4.23 (Outstanding)		
Standard Deviation	0.05 (Compressed)		

Table 4 presented the outcomes of the Teacher Performance Evaluation for the academic year 2023-2024, derived from the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). It categorized teacher performance into two main groups based on their evaluation scores. The first category, ranging from 4.1 to 5.00, represented "Outstanding" performance, with 143 teachers achieving scores within this range. This group constituted 56.75% of the total evaluated teachers, indicating a predominant presence of outstanding performance. The second category spanned from 3.1 to 4.00, denoting "Very Satisfactory" performance, with 109 teachers falling within this range, accounting for 43.25% of the evaluated teachers.

The table also provided summary statistics: the total number of teachers evaluated was 252. The mean grade, calculated at 4.23, indicated an overall high level of performance across the evaluated teachers. The standard deviation of 0.05 suggested a compressed distribution of scores around the mean, indicating consistency in the evaluation outcomes.

These findings from the IPCRF-based evaluation highlighted the majority of teachers achieving commendable ratings, predominantly in the outstanding and very satisfactory performance categories. The data underscored the effective implementation of the evaluation system in assessing and recognizing teacher performance, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the educational workforce's achievements and areas of strength.

Teacher quality, including both test scores and non-test scores, significantly impacts students' high school performance, with larger effects in later grades and core elementary subjects (Petek & Pope, 2022).

Relationship between the level of perception of the teacher-respondents as regards teachers' development and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF

Table 5. *Relationship between the level of perception of the teacher-respondents as regards teachers' development and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Perception of the teacher-respondents as regards teachers' development and Teachers' performance	0.83	0.00896	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

As written in Table 6, the correlation analysis revealed a strong relationship ($r = 0.83$, $p = 0.00896$) between the perception of teachers regarding teachers' development and teacher performance based on IPCRF evaluations. This significant correlation indicated that teachers' development, as perceived by teachers, directly influenced and contributed to teacher performance outcomes.

The rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0) in this context affirmed that there was a statistically significant association between these variables. Teachers' perceptions of administrators' leadership practices, encompassing aspects such as instructional support, resource allocation, communication effectiveness, and overall managerial competence, played a pivotal role in shaping the educational environment and supporting teacher effectiveness.

This finding underscored the importance of strong and supportive leadership in educational settings. Administrators who demonstrated effective leadership practices, as perceived by teachers, were more likely to foster a positive school climate, provide adequate resources and support, and facilitate professional growth opportunities—all of which contributed to enhanced teacher performance as evaluated through IPCRF metrics.

Investing in improving leadership practices among public-school administrators could therefore lead to improved teacher performance, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes and overall school effectiveness. This correlation highlighted the critical role that administrators' leadership plays in shaping the educational landscape and supporting the professional growth and effectiveness of teachers within their schools.

Laurel (2023) stated that educational leadership and practices significantly impact school systems and discipline, promoting reform, improving teaching quality, and fostering a safe and orderly learning environment.

Training Development Program

Table 6 outlined five distinct training and development programs that were designed to enhance teachers' professional growth and support within the school environment. Initially, the Curriculum Alignment Workshops led by the Curriculum Director, aimed to align instructional practices with the school's educational goals. These workshops provided teachers with the skills to develop and implement effective curriculum models, fostering collaboration to ensure consistency in teaching approaches across grade levels and subjects.

Table 6. *Proposed Training Development Program*

<i>Program Title / Time</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Person In Charge</i>
1. Curriculum Alignment Workshops (2025-2026)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Align instructional practices with school's educational goals and standards. - Enhance teachers' ability to develop and implement curriculum models effectively. - Foster collaboration among teachers to ensure consistency in curriculum delivery. 	Curriculum Director
2. Mentorship and Coaching Program (2025-2026)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pair experienced teachers with newer colleagues to provide guidance and support. - Share best practices and facilitate professional growth through ongoing mentorship. - Improve instructional techniques and classroom management skills. 	Professional Development Leader
3. Reflective Practice Sessions (2025-2026)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote a culture of self-reflection and continuous improvement among educators. - Provide structured time for teachers to analyze and refine their teaching strategies. - Foster collaboration through peer feedback and lesson planning sessions. 	Instructional Coach
4. Policy Advisory Committees (2025-2026)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage teachers in shaping educational policies and practices within the school. - Solicit input on curriculum development, assessment strategies, and professional development. - Ensure policies are responsive to educators' needs and aligned with instructional goals. 	Policy Coordinator
5. Technology Integration Workshops (2025-2026)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equip teachers with skills to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. - Explore innovative digital tools and platforms for personalized learning experiences. - Enhance student engagement and assessment strategies through technology. 	Technology Integration Specialist

The Mentorship and Coaching Program overseen by the Professional Development Leader, paired experienced teachers with newer colleagues. This initiative facilitated the sharing of best practices, improved instructional techniques, and supported ongoing professional growth through personalized guidance and support.

Reflective Practice Sessions, led by the Instructional Coach, promoted a culture of continuous improvement among educators. These sessions provided structured opportunities for teachers to reflect on their teaching strategies, receive peer feedback, and collaborate on lesson planning, enhancing teaching effectiveness and student engagement.

The Policy Advisory Committees coordinated by the Policy Coordinator, engaged teachers in shaping educational policies and practices. Teachers provided valuable input on curriculum development, assessment strategies, and professional development priorities, ensuring that policies were responsive to educators' needs and aligned with instructional goals.

Lastly, the Technology Integration Workshops guided by the Technology Integration Specialist, equipped teachers with skills to effectively integrate digital tools into their teaching practices. These workshops explored innovative technologies for personalized learning experiences, enhancing student engagement and improving assessment strategies through the strategic use of technology.

These programs were implemented to align with recommendations aimed at fostering collaboration, promoting reflective practices, empowering teachers in policy development, and enhancing technological integration—all crucial elements in supporting teachers' professional growth and improving educational outcomes.

Conclusions

Several key conclusions can be drawn Based on teachers' perceptions regarding public school administrators' leadership practices in promoting professional development, creating conditions for effective professional growth, and influencing policy implications. Administrators played a crucial role in supporting teachers' professional development by aligning in-service training with school goals and encouraging practical application of newly acquired skills. This approach enhanced teachers' instructional practices and improved student learning outcomes by effectively integrating innovative strategies and technologies. Administrators strategically selected professional development activities to ensure they were relevant and supportive of educational objectives, fostering a culture of continuous improvement among educators. Furthermore, administrators facilitated effective professional development by providing clear curricular models and instructional guidance. This structured approach helped teachers align their teaching practices with school

standards and promoted collaborative learning environments. By dedicating time for reflection and collaboration, administrators enabled teachers to refine their instructional methods, contributing to enhanced teaching effectiveness and student engagement.

Regarding policy implications, administrators adopted evidence-based practices and supported professional learning communities to address instructional challenges effectively. They leveraged expert teachers as mentors to enhance instructional support across the school, ensuring continuous professional growth among educators. This strategic approach not only supported teachers in achieving high standards of instructional excellence but also influenced educational policies and practices within the school system, reflecting administrators' leadership impact on systemic improvements.

The correlation between administrators' leadership practices and teachers' performance, as evaluated through IPCRF metrics, underscored the significance of supportive leadership in educational settings. Teachers perceived effective leadership as pivotal in creating a positive school climate, providing necessary resources, and facilitating professional growth opportunities—all of which contributed to high ratings in performance evaluations. This relationship highlighted the role of administrators in fostering a conducive environment where teachers thrived professionally and contributed effectively to student success.

Teachers' perceptions strongly endorse administrators' leadership in promoting professional development, creating supportive conditions for growth, and influencing educational policies. Effective leadership practices enhanced teachers' instructional capabilities and contributed to overall school effectiveness and educational outcomes. By prioritizing strategic initiatives aligned with educational goals and providing ongoing support, administrators played a crucial role in shaping a collaborative and innovative learning environment that benefited teachers and students alike.

Based on the conclusions drawn from teachers' perceptions of administrators' leadership practices, several recommendations can be made to enhance educational effectiveness and support professional growth. First, it is crucial to maintain a continuous alignment of professional development opportunities with the school's educational goals and strategic priorities. Regularly updating training programs to reflect emerging instructional trends and addressing specific needs identified through teacher feedback ensures relevance and impact. Second, expanding mentorship and coaching programs can significantly support professional growth among educators. Formalizing mentorship initiatives that pair experienced teachers with newer colleagues fosters knowledge sharing and enhances instructional practices. Third, fostering a culture of reflective practice and collaboration is essential. Providing structured time within the school schedule for teachers to engage in peer observation, feedback sessions, and collaborative lesson planning promotes continuous improvement. Fourth, empowering teachers in policy formulation enhances ownership and effectiveness. Involving teachers in committees or task forces to provide input on curriculum development, assessment strategies, and professional development priorities ensures that policies are responsive to educators' insights and needs. Lastly, investing in technological integration and innovation supports instructional effectiveness. Providing training and resources for teachers to integrate digital tools and innovative pedagogical approaches enhances student engagement and personalized learning experiences. By implementing these recommendations, administrators can strengthen their leadership practices, cultivate a supportive environment for professional growth, and ultimately improve student outcomes and overall school success.

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